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The Impact of VAAs on Aspects of Political Engagement: Insights from Panel Data Collected During The 2017 German Federal Elections Campaign

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– Draft-Version –

Abstract

So far, research on the effects of Voting Advice Applications has been primarily focused on aspects of voting behaviour, whether, for example, these online tools impact citizens' likelihood to vote or voting choices. Relatively under-researched remain questions concerning the relationship between using VAAs and other forms of political participation, such as involvement in electoral campaigns. This paper uses panel data generated in 4 waves during and after the period of the German Federal Elections in September, 2017 to examine the tendency of using a VAA to be associated with such behaviours. Results indeed suggest a positive association between VAA-use and increased consumption of politics-related media, so that using the Wahl-O-Mat VAA was contemporaneous with an increased frequency of information-seeking in other media (e.g. TV, newspapers), suggesting that the two types of behaviours might be mutually reinforcing. We additionally find a positive, though not statistically significant tendency to use the Wahl-O-Mat and participate in electoral campaigns (through e.g. attending party rallies). However, we find no evidence of an association between VAA use and increased interpersonal talk about politics or seeking of information closely related to the electoral contest, such as reading party manifestos.

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Introduction

Almost 20 years following Pharr, Putnam & Dalton's observation in 2000 that continuous commitment to democratic values among electorates notwithstanding, "by almost any measure, political alienation soared over the last three decades", politics today is faced with a similar situation. Despite democracy being the most preferred political system, discontent grows (e.g. Dahlberg et al., 2015; Norris, 2012) with increasing dissatisfaction with governments, political institutions (Bowler et al., 2007) and political parties (Dalton & Wattenberg, 2002; Mair, 2008) and, importantly, declining political participation (Putnam, 2000).

As the latter is both vital for democracy and closely connected to the concept of a public sphere, the question of engaging citizens becomes central to both the fields of political communication and political science (Dalton, 2008). The desired mobilization is postulated to be most straightforwardly achieved by increasing basic political competence among the electorate through civic education (Grönlund & Milner, 2006) and informational campaigns to engage and mobilise the body politique (Gelman & King, 1993; Iyengar & Simon, 2000; though cf. Lupia & McCubbins, 1998).

New Information & Communication Technologies (ICTs) may have a role to play in re-invigorating political interest and engagement through their capacity to multiply the availability and accessibility of information, to enable the bypassing of traditional gatekeepers, such as journalists and media experts (Blumler & Gurevitch, 2001) and to allow the transition from a low to a highly personalised media environment (Van Aelst et al., 2017). Still, as ICT effects on participation have been inconsistent over time (Bimber & Copeland, 2013) and possibly limited to individuals already more active and interested in politics (Boulianne, 2009¹) the promise of a purely technologically determined solution of the participation problem has not, as yet, been fulfilled.

¹ for a VAA-oriented discussion of the normalization/mobilization thesis see Hirzalla et al., 2010.

Still, a positive effect of increased engagement with new and social media is generally reported, particularly relating to non-traditional forms of participation (Shah, Cho, Eveland & Kwak, 2005; Boulianne, 2011 for a meta-analysis as to the internet; Skoric et al., 2016 for social media).

One particularly relevant instance of ICT application here are Voting Advice Applications (hereafter VAAs), which although existing in pen-and-paper form since 1989 (De Graaf, 2010) have seen an exponential rise in popularity since the advent of their online version. Sometimes explicitly designed to be part of civic education (as is the case with the Wahl-O-Mat examined in this paper), VAAs are online platforms operating in pre-electoral periods which prospective voters can freely visit; after declaring their agreement or disagreement on a number of policy-statements (e.g. “Same sex marriage should become institutionalised”) they are provided with measures of closeness to the political parties or candidates whose positions on the issues have been estimated beforehand in a number of different ways (e.g. by submitting questionnaires to parties and/or expert surveys etc., see Gemenis & van Ham, 2013 for an overview).

The increasing popularity of these tools is reflected in both the steadily increasing absolute number of VAA uses, occasionally in the millions (de Graaf, 2010; Marschall & Schmidt, 2010) and in terms of engaging significant portions of the electorate; Marschall (2014) reports that in 11 cases since 2010, VAA uses reach 15.3% of the respective electorates on average, up to more than 50% for the case of StemWijzer in the Netherlands in 2017 (Pajala et al., 2018, p. 702). The number of countries with a VAA available has also increased, as have the different types of elections (regional, national, transnational), covered by VAAs (Garzia & Marschall, 2012).

Mechanisms through which VAAs can be expected to impact political behaviour

Since, as per Verba, Scholzman & Brady (1995; p. 15-16), people’s political participation is inhibited by either deficits in time, money or skills, lack of interest regarding political matters or the lack of mobilization attempts, there are good theoretical reasons to postulate an impact for VAAs on individual voters’ political behaviour, although the specifics of the underlying mechanism depend on one’s broader theoretical framework (see Garzia, Trechsel & De Angelis, 2017). VAAs can, for example be expected to decrease the costs of obtaining and processing political information by gathering political party-related information under a single platform and

presenting them in a structured and personalised manner (Garzia, 2010). Alternatively, they may act to increase the utility expectation of voting by enhancing a sense of personal political competence (Fivaz & Nadig, 2010), by making the differences between parties clearer, by bypassing secondary or negative aspects of political campaigns (Walgrave et al., 2008) or by stimulating interpersonal political talk (Ladner et al., 2008; p.22), all antecedents of interest in politics and participation (Kaid, McKinney & Tedescim 2007).

Broadly speaking however, most currently theorised pathways for VAAs impact on behaviour refer to their capacity to inform voters on the number of alternatives on offer in an individualized, personally meaningful way (Walgrave et al., 2008). And, indeed, VAA users have been reported to find the tools informative (Mykkänen et al., 2007), an impetus to seek further information regarding candidates and parties (Marschall & Schmidt, 2010; though see De Rosa, 2010) and increased electoral volatility has been associated with increased VAA-use in Dutch constituencies (Kleinnijenhuis, van de Pol & Krouwel, 2017).

Moreover, political science literature has robustly connected other channels of collecting information, such as newspapers (McLeod et al., 1999), television (Norris, 1996), Internet (Shah, 2005) and mobile communication technologies (Campbell & Kwak, 2010) to increased participation. This relation between obtaining information and mobilising may not be straightforward, but rather indirect, through an increase of one's sense of confidence or efficacy (Jung, Kim, and Gil de Zúñiga, 2011) and facilitation of interpersonal (Huckfeldt & Sprague, 1995), computer- (Hardy & Scheufele, 2005) or social media-mediated communication (Gil de Zúñiga, Molyneux, & Zheng, 2014).

Much of the empirical work concerning VAAs has unsurprisingly focused primarily on VAAs' capacity to mobilise voting, as well as vote choice, not unnaturally, since the latter two consist the main impetus behind the development of most VAAs (Heinsohn et al., 2015). "Political participation" however, even when only considered in its "conventional" (Barnes & Kaase, 1979) or "institutional" (Conway, 200) forms has been greatly expanded since its original conceptualization as strictly vote casting and direct engagement with campaign activities (e.g. Lazarsfeld et al., 1948 – for a concise history of the term see van Deth, 2001). This is readily

observable in the types of questions asked in relevant surveys: Lane (1959), for example expanded the concept to include contacting officials and Verba & Nie (1972) added party-membership & related activities (e.g. attending meetings), along with interpersonal phenomena such as attempts at persuasion and raising political issues in group settings. Barnes & Kaase (1979) further included protest activities and reading about politics in newspapers while Verba et al., (1995) expanded the contacting officials category and added participation in voluntary associations (e.g. trade unions, hobby clubs etc. see also Norris, 2001).

So, adopting a definition of political participation as any activity with the “intent or effect of influencing government action- either directly by affecting the making or implementation of public policy or indirectly by influencing the selection of people who make those policies” (Verba et al., 1995; p.38), in this study we are interested in examining whether using a VAA correlates with other forms of information seeking about politics in general or the election in particular, as well as engagement with political campaigns, e.g. through attendance of party rallies.

Empirical findings concerning VAA impact on behaviour

Proving the existence of a link between VAA-use and offline individual behaviour however is challenging and as a first step we consider previous efforts to establish their impacts. The empirical work considered below has thus far been primarily based on data generated through two sources: data obtained through VAAs themselves and cross-sectional comparisons between VAA- and non-respondents to, usually national level, representative surveys. A comparably smaller body of studies has also started to accumulate data through field experiments and panel studies.

i) Studies using data solely collected through VAAs

Studies based solely on VAA-generated data, through questions in the main body or in an opt-in survey following the VAA’s results, enabling pre-post comparisons, have thus far reported the largest estimates for VAA impact, although figures tend to vary substantially between national contexts and studies. When it comes to increasing the likelihood of users casting a vote, for example, Mykkänen and Moring (2006) report a 5% increase, Marschall & Schmidt (2010) a 15% increase, while Ladner and Pianzola (2010) note that 40% of their users declared that the VAA had a “decisive influence” in driving them to the polls.

Comparably large are also self-reported impacts on vote choice, which range from 6% (Garzia & Marschall, 2012), to 8% (Alvarez, Levin, Mair & Trechsler, 2014), 10% (Kleinnijenhuis & van Hoof, 2008; p.8) etc. up to 67% (Ladner, Fivaz & Pianzola, 2012). Evidence to the contrary has also been offered, as in Walgrave et al. (2008), where 90% of users explicitly denied that the VAA had any effect on their vote; similarly, Wall, Krouwel & Vitiello (2014) report that even in cases where the tool offered a suggestion very much in line with existing pre-dispositions, users often did not follow it. Examining a less well-studied aspect, impact on political knowledge, Ladner (2012) documented that 84% of users reported an increase in their amount of knowledge about the election (see also Kamoen et al., 2015; Dumont & Kies, 2012; Ladner et al., 2009).

While important, especially if comparative, these studies suffer an important methodological drawback when it comes to establishing VAA effects; they only involve information from a group that was entirely self-selected (i.e. voters who used the respective VAA and who opted in to participate in a follow-up survey). This can be a problem firstly in terms of representativeness of findings, as VAA users are known to be significantly different from the underlying population (e.g. predominately male, more educated, see Hirzalla et al., 2010; Marschall, 2014) due to both non-coverage bias and selection effects. Since in many instances users voluntarily took part in the onsite-surveys, a secondary selection bias comes into the picture, given that those who tend to take part in (online) surveys are usually different from the average user. Apart from the selection biases, attributing any result to the impact of the tool is only tentative, since there is no reference group (non-users) in order to establish a baseline for the effect.

ii) Cross-sectional comparisons

The inclusion of questions concerning VAA use in nationally representative surveys, such as the GLES (“German Longitudinal Election Study”) in Germany, has enabled VAA researchers to compare between users and non-users, in addition to allowing for an amelioration of selection effects by statistically controlling for the effect of variables known to differ between the two groups, such as education and interest in politics.

A number of studies in this vein, report a more moderate but existing difference between the two groups when it comes to likelihood to vote, although the range of effects remains large. While Ruusuvirta & Rosema (2009; p.18) for example report a 3% difference, Marschall & Schultze (2012) report 6%, and Garzia, Trechsel & De Angelis (2016) 16%. Similarly, Fivaz & Nadig (2010) find a 5% increase across different national contexts, and in similar fashion, Dinas, Trechsel & Vassil (2011) report a 14% difference on average.

Relating to vote choice, Mykkänen, Moring, & Pehkonen, (2007, p. 5) report a probability of 15% to follow the advice of the VAA, if the respondent had no initial preference, which drops to 3% for people with pre-existing choices. Ladner et al. (2010) and Ruusuvirta & Rosema (2009) also report similar evidence of vote switching, although panel data suggest that this effect is likely short-lived – Wallgrave et al., 2008; Enyedi, 2015). A number of studies (Marschall, 2014; Hirzalla et al., 2011; Dumont & Kies, 2012) also find differences on the levels of political interest between the two groups and Schultze (2014; p.41) reports increased political knowledge among VAA users as to party positions, corroborated by Westle, Begemann & Rütter (2015 - although the latter used a pre-post survey design rather than cross-sectional comparisons).

These studies using data collected from nationally representative surveys allow for a clearer picture of impacts, since an appropriate reference group is used for comparison. Coverage and selection effects remain present however, and, as such, attribution of any difference to the effect of the tool and not to the composition of the sample under study is tenuous, as even when statistically controlling for the latter, an amount of un-measured or un-observable heterogeneity between the groups can be expected to persist (Gemenis & Rosema, 2014; Pianzola, 2014). The latter two studies attempted to account for this problem by explicitly modelling these selection effects statistically either through propensity score matching (Gemenis & Rosema, 2014) or Heckman selection models (Pianzola, 2014), with the former concluding an (expected) difference of 4.4% in turnout as a function of using a VAA, while the latter a statistically significant, though small, increased probability to switch vote after using a VAA.

iii) Field experiments

In order to bypass the issue of self-selection into treatment, a number of studies have more recently attempted to gauge VAA effects by randomly assigning individuals to either a treatment (VAA) or control (non-VAA) conditions. Enyedi (2016) using this method, for example, describes no significant differences on electoral turnout between the groups, though Vassil (2011) reports a 13% increase among his student sample.

In agreement with the latter, Garzia, Trechsel & De Angelis (2016) used a pre-post design along with random assignment and report an increased likelihood to vote of 10.7% for participants who used a VAA compared to those who did not. Evidence from this avenue (random assignment plus pre-post comparisons) regarding vote choice suggests that only a small effect can be expected, if any, and it is likely not to be durable (Mahéo, 2016; Enyedi, 2015). It should be mentioned however that this metric (vote switching) for gauging an effect for VAAs might be somewhat strict; Pianzola et al. (2012) using Probability To Vote for each individual party as the measure, rather than Vote Intention, for example, suggest that users altered the likelihood to vote for respective parties, even if they did not switch voting preference altogether.

Assuming appropriately random assignment to control and treatment/experimental conditions is a good way to control the effect of un-observed confounders, as the VAA and non-VAA groups can be expected to be similar as to a number of critical parameters (e.g. political interest) by chance alone. However, this kind of research can be expensive, limited in scope and generally involves a trade-off between ecological validity and control of spurious effects.

iv) Panel studies

Only a small amount of studies have used panel data, usually as part of a larger design, (e.g. Mahéo, 2016; Enyedi, 2015; Garzia et al., 2016 as described above). In a pure panel study, Heinsohn et al. (2015) found an increased tendency for VAA use to be positively correlated with increased interest in the electoral campaigns, as well as increased political knowledge. Very similar to the design in Heinsohn et al., the present study uses data obtained from a panel study of respondents sampled to be representative as to the German online population, to study associations between using a VAA and other facets of political participation.

Panel data refers to repeated observations (e.g. a questionnaire) of the same individual in “waves”, i.e. over a relatively short period of time. Being identical to cross-sectional surveys, with an added time element, these designs share their merits but have the additional advantage of, at least partially controlling for unobserved heterogeneity between individuals, since each respondent serves as their own “control” group (Allison, 2009; p.1), while, in addition, the temporal element allows for the examination of more complicated questions over social processes and causal “effects” (Vaisey & Miles, 2014 – see “Analyses” subsection of the Method section, below). However, they also share the disadvantage of attempting to establish the effect of a “treatment” (here, using a VAA) by examining the effect on the “treated” (VAA-users) and are thus, not completely free from selection effects.

The present study

In summary then, it is difficult to avoid the conclusion that more data is needed at this point to establish if not the presence, the magnitude of impacts that VAAs might have on voters’ likelihood to turn out to the ballot and voting decisions. Yet less is known about the relationship of VAAs with other aspects of Verba & Nie’s multidimensional conceptualization of participation (1972), campaigning, communal and elite-contacting activities or with antecedents of political behaviour such as political interest or knowledge. In the study at hand, we use panel data to examine the relationship between using a VAA (the Wahl-O-Mat VAA in this instance) and, on the one hand, involvement with electoral campaigns, e.g. attending party rallies, and on the other information-seeking activities, either through the mass media or interpersonal communication.

Assuming Van de Pol et al.’s (2014; p.403-404) observation that the majority (58%) of users are “efficacious checkers”, highly interested in politics and electoral campaigns is correct, we can expect some positive association between using a VAA and engaging in other election-related behaviours. Moreover, if VAAs do act in a political knowledge enhancing capacity, previous research suggests that increased media exposure is associated with other similar behaviours (Eveland & Scheufele, 2000), as well as engagement with political campaigns (Cutts & Fieldhouse, 2009) and voter mobilisation (e.g. Livingstone & Markham, 2008). Using a VAA itself may be

seen as part of an information-seeking process, especially if considering the “checkers” who use a VAA as the endpoint of their political investigations and, thus, we expect that:

H1: Using the Wahl-O-Mat will be associated with an increased likelihood in engagement within electoral campaigns.

Furthermore, van de Pol et al. (ibid) find that a third of his users were “seekers”, looking for assistance in deciding their vote, who, while not generally interested in politics, are not pessimistic about their ability to influence politics. If that is the case, then the VAA output might indeed be used as a starting or end-point for the collection of more information (Garzia, 2010), leading to more political information-seeking behaviours. Hence, our expectations is that:

H2: Using the Wahl-O-Mat will be associated with an increased likelihood to seek information specifically about the electoral contest.

&

H3: Using the Wahl-O-Mat will be associated with an increased frequency of politics-related media consumption.

Finally, as Marschall (2011) reports that more than 70% of people who tried the German Wahl-O-Mat, used the tool’s output as an opportunity to discuss politics with their social circle (see also Ladner et al., 2008), we accordingly, expected that:

H4: Using the Wahl-O-Mat will be associated with an increased tendency to talk about politics with others.

Method

Dataset

This paper draws on panel data collected in four waves around the period of the latest German federal elections on September, 24th, 2017.² The collection process was organized and conducted by Respondi, a market research company and provided a sample approximating the German general population in terms of demographic characteristics. As such, prior to the first wave, quotas were calculated on the basis of population distributions as to age³, sex and place of residence⁴ to take

² We owe a debt of gratitude to the Fritz Thyssen Foundation/Köln which generously funded the panel study.

³ It should be noted that age was limited to be 18-69 (i.e. no participants were older than 70 years of age)

⁴ Separating participants from each German federal state

advantage of the approximately 90,000 members-strong Respondi access panel, certified as to international quality norms concerning recruitment and questioning (ISO 26362).

As mentioned above, the data collection took place in four waves lasting overall about three and a half months, including the period before (waves 1 & 2) and immediately after the election (wave 3), as well as the post-election period (wave 4), all waves lasting for about 9 days. The first wave was initiated on August, 21st, before campaigning was in full swing and ended on August, 29th, a day prior to the Wahl-O-Mat VAA becoming available to the public. It was followed by the second wave two weeks later, starting on September 14th and lasting until September 23rd, a day before the federal election on the 24th, participants having access to the Wahl-O-Mat for a minimum of two weeks. The third wave took place immediately after the elections between September 25th and October, 3rd, allowing for the examination of short-term effects and late adopters of the VAA. The final wave was conducted post-electorally between November, 27th, and December, 6th, 2017 to examine longer lasting effects.

Sample

In absolute terms, 2,380 people were recruited for the panel, although only 1,120 participated in all four surveying waves, resulting in an attrition rate of 52.9%. Since the analyses included here are based on balanced panels (i.e. participants with a full set of responses on all 4 waves), all statistics reported refer to these 1,120 participants only. Table 1 shows the demographic makeover of the sample used for the quotas, suggesting an over-representation of older participants in the panel. Focusing on the larger discrepancies, individuals in the panel aged between 18-29 were 7.8% less than what would be expected from the population, while older participants were over-represented by 6.3%, largely the effects of increased attrition for younger respondents, despite the study being fully conducted online. Men were also slightly over-represented by 1.9%, although geographic dispersion was satisfactory. It is then important to note that, given the age constraint on the panel and the aforementioned distributions, the dataset is only an approximation rather than fully representative of the population as to the three demographics.

Table 1: Sample demographics compared to the German general population

Age	Census [%]	Panel [%]	Δ	Sex	Census [%]	Panel [%]	Δ
18-29	20,81	13,0	-7,81	Male	50,02	51,9	+1,88
30-39	17,35	16,7	-0,65	Female	49,98	48,1	-1,88
40-49	24,39	21,3	-3,09	Region	Census [%]	Panel [%]	Δ
50-59	21,24	26,4	+5,16	East	15,9	15,3	-0,6
60-69 ¹	16,21	22,6	+6,39	West	84,1	84,7	+0,6

¹ Individuals under 18 or over 69 years were not part of the sample

Procedure

Individuals who indicated their willingness to participate in this study were sent 1-2 invitation emails during each data collection period and were asked to complete an online questionnaire concerning their political behaviour and attitudes, with, for the most part structured, questions ranging from socio-demographics to political party preferences and use and assessment of VAAs. Responses were given in a self-completing capacity, completion time was between 25-45 minutes and respondents were monetarily compensated for their participation.

Variables & Operationalisation

i) Dependent variables

a) Politics-related Media Consumption

A composite index calculated using responses to a number of questions asking respondents to indicate how often, on a scale from 0 (Never) to 7 (Daily), they used a number of different media (TV, newspapers, radio, internet) to inform themselves about politics – see Appendix I. Although the items used were, expectedly, well correlated, we decided not to combine them into an additive index or factor score, particularly in light of the response categories offered. The reasoning is that they are not independent behaviours satisfying a latent need but rather alternative means for achieving the same. As such, someone could conceivably satisfy the need for information through a single medium and any additive index then risks “disadvantaging” people who prefer single-channel media consumption, although it might be reasonable to assume that multi-source information seeking points to a greater need for information. As an example, consider three

respondents A, B and C, with respective responses [7, 6, 0], [7, 0, 0] and [4, 4, 0]; any additive, weighted or not, score is likely to order A first, followed by C (e.g. score:= 4+4+0 = 8) above B (7+0+0 = 7)⁵, which is likely not reflective of their willingness to consume more politics-related media, after all, B has a daily interest on the matter.

In order to calculate a composite index from these items we use a method devised by Wittkowski et al. (2004; described in easier terms in Diana, 2012) that allows for the combination of ordinal measures using a partial ordering of responses (μ -scores) to all items under the following rule: compare every respondent with every other respondent in a pair-wise manner and order them so that in any given pair, the respondent on top is the one with at least one higher value in the array of items/responses than the other; then order the sample and assign to each person a value (μ -score) equal to the number of respondents with lower values. This scheme would order the three respondents in the example appropriately: A, then B (since his second response is 0 compared to A's 6), then C (since both A & B have one higher value). However, the considerable loss in interpretability compared to an additive index should be noted, as μ -values range from $[-N -1]$: $[N+1]$.

b) Politics-related Interpersonal Talk

The tendency to engage in interpersonal talk with others about politics was operationalised as the response to a single item, "How often do use personal conversations to inform yourself about politics (0: Never to 7: Daily)⁶ – see Appendix I.

c) Election-related Information Seeking

Three questions in the survey concerned information seeking on matters related strictly to the upcoming election (e.g. watching the televised debate, reading party manifestos) with only "Yes/No" possible responses and a simple additive score was calculated for the total number of such behaviours each respondent engaged in⁷.

⁵ Median-based ordering would produce the same outcome

⁶ Analyses using a similar question: "How often do you talk politics with your friends and acquaintances?" provided for similar findings and have been omitted

⁷ As was the case for questions over engagement with the electoral campaigns, these questions were only asked at waves 2 and 3.

d) Engagement with Electoral Campaign

A composite index calculated from responses to 4 items concerning activities such as attending party rallies or being actively involved in the campaign (“Yes/No”) – see Appendix I for details. Since most respondents (84.6%) engaged in none of the behaviours mentioned here, a binary score was calculated with 1 if the respondent engaged in any such activity.⁸

ii) Independent variable: VAA-use

The independent variable for this study is whether respondents actually used the Wahl-O-Mat VAA prior to the 2017 German federal election (“Yes / No”). Since the VAA was not available when the first wave of data collection took place, values for all respondents for this wave were set at “No”.

iii) Control variables

Panel-data specific analyses enable the implicit controlling of time-invariant characteristics (such as sex or education), however time-variant variables that can potentially affect the relationship between dependent and independent variables need to be explicitly controlled and for this purpose we included in our models 4 additional indices that have either been shown or can be reasonably expected to affect the dependent variables (see Eveland et al., 2005; Shah & Sheufele, 2006; Sotirovic & McLeod, 2001):

a) Political Interest: Responses to a single item asking respondents how interested they are in politics on a five-point scale (“Not at all” to “Very strongly”).

b) Political knowledge: Calculated as the total number of correct responses to three factual questions (e.g. “What is the electoral threshold (%) to enter the Bundestag”), with missing values being treated as incorrect responses.

c) Efficacy: Efficacy refers to a citizens’ sense of adequacy to comprehend political issues as well as their sense that the political system is responsive to their needs and amenable to their actions. We initially tested the 10 dedicated items in question for uni-dimensionality, but found it not to be

⁸ Note that questions for categories a) and d) were only asked in panel waves 2 and 3.

the case and a separate index was calculated for internal (akin here to self-confidence on political matters) and external efficacy (closer here to cynicism toward politicians and parties – see Appendix I). For each, a regression-based factor score was calculated, independently within each wave, through Factor Analysis using polychoric correlations and ML estimation.

Analyses

Panel data-based analyses operate on the logic that effects on any variable of interest at the individual level are a function of: a) Events that affect all individuals simultaneously, b) Observable and measured time-invariant characteristics (e.g. sex), c) unobservable or unmeasured time-invariant characteristics (e.g. genetic makeup), d) Observable and measured time-variant characteristics (for example, interest in politics can be expected to increase in periods closer to elections), and e) unobservable or unmeasured time-variant characteristics (in addition to interactions between a and b:e).

The primary purpose of panel data is exactly to help control measured and un-measured time-invariant variables (Halaby, 20014; p.508) which is achieved by relying on parameter estimation within individuals, rather than between-groups (i.e. using the person themselves as control). Although a number of different configurations for analyses (e.g. Lagged Dependent Variable models, First Differences models) are available, the most straightforward way (and the approach taken here) is through “Fixed effects models” or “Panel regressions”, where either the intercept for the regression model, its coefficients or both are allowed to vary between different individuals, the former allowing a different baseline per person, the latter allowing for some but not full control of time-variant unobserved variables. As both F-ratio tests and Hausman specification tests were statistically significant for all models tested (see Tables 2 & 3 below), all regressions reported here are of the random intercept, fixed slopes/coefficients type.

All analyses were conducted using the R statistical software and more specifically the psych package (Revelle, 2017) for factor extraction, the plm (Croissant, 2017) and lme4 (Bates, 2017) packages for panel regressions and the muStat package (Wittkowski, Song & Bigio, 2010) for the calculation of μ -scores.

Results

Using panel data collected in 4 waves between one month prior to and two months following the German federal election of 2017, we attempt to examine the relationship between using a Voting Advice Application and: involvement with electoral campaigns, political media consumption, interpersonal discourse about politics and information-seeking specifically related to the election at hand (e.g. reading party manifestos). We proceed by providing some descriptive statistics, prior to presenting the regression models employed.

Descriptives

Of the group of 1,099 respondents, 575 reported to have used the Wahl-O-Mat during the election campaign while 524 had not. Remarkably, more than 52% of the sample resorted to the tool, indicating the enormous popularity of this – in absolute numbers – most demanded VAA in Europe (for the 2017 version, about 15,7 million usages were registered accounting for an all-time high). Within the group of users, we distinguish between “early” and “late adopters”, depending on whether respondents used the tool before the second wave or between the second and the third wave. The group of late adopters was rather small ($n = 82$) accounting for about 14% of the users, while the overwhelming share all of the VAA users were early adopters ($n = 493$).

a) Politics-related Media Consumption

For ease of presentation in the descriptives section, instead of μ -scores, we report statistics based on a single column created by combining responses to the 4 items and holding, per participant the highest value in the array of responses (i.e. for each person, the value for the medium most frequently used). We find that on average respondents were quite keen to look for political information through their most preferred medium, reporting engaging in such behaviour between 5 and 6 days a week (pooled mean= 5.66 - see Figure 1). This high tendency is maintained across waves with small deviations, although there seems to be a drop for respondents who used the VAA at wave 3 (“late adopters”). Differences between the three groups (non-VAA users, early and late adopters) were small as the largest discrepancy was between early and late VAA-adopters (about 0.5 pts. on a 7-pt scale). As mentioned above however, the group of late VAA adopters was quite small, hence the large standard errors observable in all graphs.

Figure 1. Frequency of Political Media Consumption over

Scale adapted for the graph; original scale range 0:7

b) Politics-related Interpersonal Talk

Figure 2 plots the frequency of engaging in interpersonal discussion about politics with others across the 4 waves. Again we find limited variability across time, although there is a small drop between waves 1 and 4 for all groups, though the differences are small in size (0.28 of a 7-pt scale on average). Observable is also the about 0.5 pt.-large difference on average between early VAA adopters and non-users (meaning about 7% less interpersonal political talk). More surprising however is the overall small frequency of talking about politics with friends and acquaintances (pooled average of 2.55 days a week), although since this was an online panel, it is not unreasonable to assume that some of this activity takes place online (not in “personal conversations”).

Figure 2. Frequency of Interpersonal Political Talk over

Scale adapted for the graph; original scale range 0:7

c) Election-related Information Seeking

Figure 3 plots the average number of election-related information seeking activities that respondents reported engaging in across the 2 waves where the relevant questions were asked. Given that the questions referred to not particularly costly behaviours (e.g. watching the televised political leaders debate), engagement of this sort can be considered average (pooled average 1.4 out of a maximum score of 3) and differs little between the two waves. At the group level though, non-VAA users appear to be considerably less likely to engage in these activities (by 0.43 points, i.e. 15% less on average).

Figure 3. Election-related Information Seeking across Waves 2 &

d) Engagement with Electoral Campaign

Similarly, respondents in this study generally appeared to have little interest to partake in campaign activities, with only about 14.7% probability on average to engage in any of the 4 behaviours tested and although nearly VAA-users were 5% more likely to participate, the average remains rather low (about 18% across the two waves).

Figure 4. Likelihood of Engagement with Electoral Campaigns across Waves 2 & 3

Scale adapted for the graph; original scale range 0:1

“Difference-In-Differences” (DID) models that compare the rate of change between groups as the timeline moves forward after the two VAA-user groups were pooled together, provide some weak support to the intuitions described above. In the case of interpersonal political talk for example, the difference between VAA and non-VAA users is statistically significant ($b = 0.36, p < .001$) and more interestingly, so is the term for wave 3 ($b = -0.33, p = .03$) suggesting that people of both groups avoided talking about politics in the two weeks immediately before the election. In all other cases, the DID model predictions failed to reach statistical significance, with the exception of information-seeking about the election, where VAA-users were significantly more likely to engage in such behaviour ($b = 0.33, p < .001$).

DID models are generally helpful in detecting the effect of some external event (such as a new policy or law), however they remain between-group comparisons, suffering from the selection effects and do not take full advantage of the repeated observations over the same person⁹. So, in order to examine whether the act of visiting the Wahl-O-Mat was temporally associated with a

⁹ Also note that the interaction terms in all cases, i.e. the “difference in differences” terms (here the VAA effect terms) were in every case non-significant.

change in one of the variables of interest, we proceed to the Fixed Effects (Panel) regression models¹⁰.

A final note is warranted on descriptives. Perhaps the most interesting aspect here is the observation that early VAA adopters, also tend to peak at wave 2 and drop off by wave 3 for other types of behaviours as well, while the reverse seems to be true for late adopters. In fact this tendency is marginally non-significant for media consumption and significant for interpersonal talk, i.e. people who use the VAA more than two weeks prior to the election, also consume more politics-related media and talk about politics more in the same period and significantly less so in the next period of time ($\chi^2(1) = 2.73, p = .1$ and $\chi^2(1) = 5.63, p = .017$, respectively).

Regression Models

a) Politics-related Media Consumption

Shifting our focus on modelling, Table 2 summarises the findings from both simple (Columns A) and full models (Columns B) for media consumption and interpersonal political talk. We find a statistically significant positive association between VAA use and mass media consumption about politics¹¹ ($F(6,2832) = 6.26, p < .001; b = 18.5, p = .02$), even after controlling for the effect of interest in politics, political knowledge and efficacy. Of the latter, only self-reported interest in politics had a statistically significant effect, in line with previous findings that individuals who consume more political content on both mass media (Norris, 1996; McLeod et al., 1999) as well as the internet (Shah, Kwak & Holbert, 2000) tend to engage more in other such behaviours and generally be more socially and politically engaged (Livingstone & Markham, 2008)¹². However, the strong but not statistically significant association between media consumption and both forms of political efficacy should also be noted.

¹⁰ Note that in all cases the regressions reported here are: random intercept, fixed slope mixed models, see table 2 for F-ratio test of poolability and Hausman specification test.

¹¹ Approximated using μ -scores

¹² Though note that digital media use is frequently a significant but weak predictor of institutional political participation (Bimber & Copeland, 2013)

Table 2. Panel Regression for Political Media Consumption & Political Talk (W1: W4)

	Politics-related Media Consumption						Politics-related Interpersonal Talk					
	Model a			Model b			Model a			Model b		
	coef.	std. err.	p	coef.	std. err.	p	coef.	std. err.	p	coef.	std. err.	p
VAA use	20.71	7.88	.008	18.5	7.9	.02	-0.01	0.05	.84	-0.02	0.05	.77
Political Interest				41.5	9	<.001				0.14	0.06	.018
Political Knowledge				-9.35	20.98	.65				-0.05	0.14	.69
Internal Efficacy				15.6	8.49	.066				0.15	0.05	.008
External Efficacy (Cynicism)				-14	7.41	.059				-0.12	0.05	.011
Avg. Intercept	47.2			-94.6			2.7			2.23	0.049	
Model Fit	F(1,2837)=6.9, p=.009			F(6,2832)=6.26, p<.001			F(1,2852)= 0.87, p=.91			F(6,2832)= 4.66, p=.001		
R ² _{GLMM}	.002			.08			<.001			.08		
F-test (full model)	F(950,2832) = 11.57, p < .001						F (950,2832) = 7.26, p < .001					
Hausman test	x ² (6) = 142.47, p < .001						x ² (6) = 73.4, p < .001					

b) Politics-related Interpersonal Talk

Having observed an association between VAA-use and media consumption, we further examined its relationship to interpersonal talk about politics, which substantial literature suggests is the main avenue through which media exert influence on political participation (i.e. the Communications Mediation Model; see McLeod et al., 1996; Sotirovic & McLeod, 2001). We find that although the overall model presents a significant fit ($F(6,2832) = 4.66, p = .001$), VAA use is not at all a good predictor of increased frequency of interpersonal communication ($b = -.02, p = .77$). Political interest and both aspects of political efficacy, on the other hand, are, with respondents engaging in interpersonal political talk more frequently if they were more interested in politics, more confident about their capacity to engage with the matter and less cynical about politicians' and parties' consideration of the electorate.

c) Election-related Information Seeking

Information-seeking specifically about the elections refers to a category of variables concerning behaviours such as reading party manifestos, watching the televised debates etc., in other words consuming informational content that is most like what VAAs offer. To our surprise then, this was the model that provided the least fit overall ($F(6,495) = 0.74$, $p = .615$) with none of the predictors included in the model being associated with engaging in these types of behaviours.

Very tentatively extending the finding that the primary source of information for voters is not debates or news, but rather political advertising (Just et al., 1990; Kaid, 2004; Brians & Wattenberg, 1996) we suggest that, at least in this case, using the Wahl-O-Mat might have acted as an alternative of such behaviours, e.g. reading party manifestos (or the reverse), rather than in a complementary fashion. However, some care should be taken not to over-extend findings from this and the following model; as mentioned in the method section, the relevant variables were only measured on waves 2 and 3 and, as such, the only group with a reliable control baseline (i.e. without having used the VAA already) are late adopters¹³, a group small ($n = 83$) and perhaps, in some ways, more volatile, group of VAA-users than early adopters.

d) Engagement with Electoral Campaign

Finally, we find the propensity of respondents to engage in any of the three examined campaign related activities (e.g. party rallies) to be positively associated with visiting the Wahl-O-Mat, though to a marginally non-significant degree ($b = 1.73$, $p = .074$). This positive but not strong or systematic enough association between VAA use and electoral engagement was enhanced by the inclusion in the model of the remaining control predictors, although of the latter, only internal political efficacy (i.e. confidence in one's ability to engage in politics) was a significant predictor of involvement with the campaigns.

¹³ Early VAA adopters were dropped from these models

Table 3. Regression for Electoral Information-Seeking & Engagement with Campaigns (W2 & 3)

	Election-related Information Seeking						Engagement with Electoral Campaign					
	Simple Model			Full Model			Simple Model			Full Model		
	coef.	std. err.	p	coef.	std. err.	p	coef.	std. err.	p	coef.	std. err.	p
VAA use	0.03	0.09	0.74	0.014	0.09	.88	1.4	0.68	.107	1.73	.97	.074
Political Interest				0.022	0.06	.72				-0.08	0.52	.87
Political Knowledge				0.07	0.14	.59				2.22	2.11	.29
Internal Efficacy				0.06	0.06	.27				1.06	0.52	.04
External Efficacy (Cynicism)				0.05	0.05	.28				-0.52	0.41	.21
Avg. Intercept	1.3			1.18			-9.7			-12.09		
Model Fit	F(1,500)=.1, p=.742			F(6,495)=0.74, p=.615			LogL=-233.5			LogL= -227.7		
R ² _{GLMM}	.001			.09			Null model LogL= -234.68					
F-test (full model)	F(500,495) = 6.25, p < .001						F (500,495) = 8.21, p < .001					
Hausman test	x ² (6) = 22.84, p < .001						x ² (6) = 16.3, p < .001					

Concluding Remarks

From their inception, VAAs were tools expected to enhance voter mobilisation through their capacity to collect, organise and make personally relevant political information in pre-electoral periods. They are hypothesised to operate through a number of different avenues, ultimately summarisable into reducing participation costs or increasing the perceived utility of voting, i.e. by affecting the “time” and “skills” aspects of Verba & Nie’s Resource Model for Participation (1972). Empirical research thus far been unequivocal with VAA-effects remaining evasive and highly dependent on time and national & electoral contexts, studied mainly with reference to vote casting and vote choice.

The present paper similarly tries to address the question whether VAAs have an impact on political engagement and sophistication, although the variables of interest are less examined aspects of

Verba & Nie's multidimensional conceptualization of participation¹⁴. Using panel data we first try to examine the association of VAA-use with politics-related media consumption, as well as, with more election-specific information seeking behaviours. We additionally look at the relationship between VAA-use and interpersonal discussions about politics and engagement with the electoral campaigns that is not voting per-se.

We find evidence for a positive relationship between consumption of politics-related media and VAA-use, an effect that is partly shared but not fully attributable to interest in politics and efficacy. It seems that in this case at least, VAA-use was part of a nexus of behaviours aimed, presumably, at satisfying the need for one to be informed and knowledgeable about politics, so that engaging in one information-seeking activity of this type acts in a reinforcing fashion toward other similar behaviours (as per Norris' "virtuous cycle").

We also find a positive tendency for association between VAA use and involvement with electoral campaigns (e.g. attending party rallies), although the relationship does not reach statistical significance. We tentatively suggest that this association is likely to be more reflective of the tendency of late VAA adopters, the only group tested for this comparison, to engage in any election-related activity (including the VAA) late in the electoral cycle than any causal link. On the other hand, we fail to obtain evidence as to such an association with interpersonal talk about politics or information-seeking about the campaign, the latter moreover being uncorrelated with any of the predictors used here (political knowledge, interest and efficacy).

Some care should be taken however when interpreting these findings, since inferences are made by contrasting individuals who, ultimately, have elected to use the VAA in the first place (i.e. are self-selected into the "treatment" condition) to non-users; that is, what is being investigated is the hypothesised effect a VAA has on VAA-users (Average Treatment effect on the Treated), rather than the counterfactual VAA effect on random individuals from the population (Average Treatment Effect). Moreover, it is important to keep in mind both the limitations of the representativeness of the sample used here, as described in the method section and the frequent volatility of findings concerning the relationships between political engagement through digital media and traditional

¹⁴ Voting, Campaign activity, Communal activities and citizen-initiated contacts – (1972, p.48)

political participation (see Bimber, 2003; Boulianne, 2009) and, as such, these findings might not be replicable in different times or national contexts, particularly where VAAs are not as popular as in Germany.

A final drawback, and possible site of expansion, of the analytical choices made here (regression models with random intercepts and fixed slopes) is the inability to examine the effect of other personal characteristics, such as age, on the relationships between the variables of interest described above. Since political participation varies by sex, education etc. (Stolle & Hooghe, 2009; Conway 2001) and VAAs produce different effects on people with different e.g. age (Ladner et al., 2012) or education (Gemenis & Rosema, 2014; Vassil, 2011), it might be interesting to re-organise the analyses to include the possibility to examine such effects (e.g. employ Allison's hybrid model [2009; p.23-25]).

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Appendix I: Variables & Operationalisation

Dependent Variables		
Variable	Measurement	Measurement Level
Politics-related Media Consumption	How often do you use the following sources to inform yourself about politics?	0:= “Never” : 7:= “Daily”
	Television	
	Newspapers	
	Radio	
Politics-related Interpersonal Talk	How often do you use the following sources to inform yourself about politics?	
	Personal conversations	
Election-related Information Seeking	Have you read election ads from parties in newspapers or magazines?	Yes / No
	Did you watch the TV duel between Angela Merkel and Martin Schulz?	
	Did you read the election program of one or more political parties?	
Engagement with Electoral Campaign	Have you attended election events or rallies of parties?	Yes / No
	Did you attend a campaign or rally?	
	Have you visited a campaign stand by a party or a candidate?	
	Are you actively involved in the ongoing campaign of a particular party?	
Independent Variable		
VAA-use	Have you already made use of the Wahl-O-Mat for the 2017 federal election?	Yes / No
Control Variables		
Political Interest	Generally speaking, how interested would you say you are about politics?	0:= “Not at all” : 5:= “Very much so”
Political Knowledge	What is the crucial vote for deciding Parliament seats?	Multiple choice
	What is the electoral threshold for entering the Bundestag?	Open-ended
	Who elects the Federal Chancellor	Multiple choice
Efficacy		
Internal	I understand political issues well.	1:= “I completely disagree” : 5:= “I completely agree”
	I am comfortable taking part in political discussions.	
	Politics has become so complicated that, as a citizen, I often do not understand what it is about.	
External	Politicians care about what ordinary people think.	
	The politicians strive for close contact with the population.	
	The parties only want the votes of the voters, their views	
Excluded from either	Today's problems are too complicated for politics to solve them	
	It is the duty of every citizen to be a regular voter	
	A single vote makes no difference in elections.	
	Politicians should take popular opinion more into account	
	In the current political climate, how big are the differences between the parties?	

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